

CAUSES OF PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Pneumonia has become one of the most urgent problems today. Despite the great progress made in the treatment of this disease, it is still one of the main causes of death. This article discusses on the causes of pneumonia in children.*

Keywords: *pneumonia; respiratory organs; infection; treatment.*

Various viruses and staphylococcal infection, as well as viral-bacterial pathogens, are distinguished. If the expected result does not come when treated with antibiotics, then the situation is serious. This is especially the case with yeast infections caused by several types of bacteria. Its frequent occurrence in young children is related to the anatomical and physiological characteristics of the respiratory organs. Pneumonia is a serious disease. To better understand what happens in the lungs and the body, we will focus on the anatomy and physiology of the lungs. The lungs are located in the chest. Each breast is divided into segments.

The right lung consists of three segments, the left lung consists of two segments. Because it is located above the heart, the left lung is about 10% smaller than the right. Lungs consist of bronchial tree and alveoli. The bronchial tree, in turn, consists of bronchi. Bronchi come in different sizes (calibers). That is, it extends from the large caliber to the small bronchi: this is called the bronchial tree. It serves to pass air during inhalation and exhalation. The bronchioles become smaller in diameter, pass into the respiratory bronchioles and finally end in the alveolar sac. The wall of the alveoli is well supplied with blood, which allows gas exchange. The alveoli is covered with a special substance (surfactant) from the inside. It serves to protect against microbes, expel microbes and microscopic dust.

Pneumonia is slightly more severe in children than in adults. The reason is that their immune system is not well developed, so the body temperature may not rise in children. In such cases, prudence is required from parents. Also, due to the fact that mucociliary clearance is not well developed in children, first there is a dry cough, and then there are cases of rapid transmission of the infection to the lungs.

Dry and moist crackles are heard on lung auscultation. When the symptoms of this disease are detected in a child, it is necessary to consult a doctor. Because pneumonia is a long-lasting disease compared to SARS. In order to determine the inflammatory process in the lungs, various examinations are carried out: blood, urine analysis, S-reactive protein in the blood, determination of procalcitonin, chest X-ray are among them. Medicines used in pneumonia are different and complex in nature, they are used to overcome the causes of the disease (etiologic therapy), eliminate the symptoms of the disease (symptomatic therapy), as well as to restore the system of body organs (supportive therapy).

At the same time, hypoallergenic diet, oxygen therapy, air humidification and room ventilation, vitamin D, immunozinc, antiviral, mucolytic and expectorant drugs, antibacterial treatment according to the instructions, drugs to improve peripheral blood circulation, such as immunoglobulin G in severe cases, are used to treat the disease. procedures are carried out.

Pneumonia is an inflammation of the lungs, which belongs to the category of acute infectious diseases. Pneumonia can be caused by viruses, bacteria and fungi. There are also types such as aspiration pneumonia and paracancer pneumonia, which develops around the center of a cancerous tumor in the lung tissue.

As soon as the first symptoms of pneumonia appear, you should immediately consult a doctor. The inflammatory process of the lungs is a serious disease that can have a negative impact on health. Before the discovery of antibiotics, pneumonia had an 80% mortality rate. Currently, the death rate due to the development of pneumonia in different regions reaches 5-40%, mainly severe complications occur in the elderly. If pneumonia is detected in time and the necessary treatment measures are applied, the disease will be cured in 10-14 days and will not leave any complications.

Modern drugs help prevent serious complications and treat almost any form of pneumonia without complications. At the same time, remember that for effective treatment and successful prevention of complications, the treatment of this disease must be carried out by a specialist. Pneumonia is an inflammatory process in lung tissues. In many cases, the cause of the disease is infections. There are different ways of infection entering the body: most often through airborne droplets, in rare cases - through blood.

Some of the microorganisms responsible for the development of pneumonia are always present in the human body. When the level of immune protection is normal, it successfully fights against such infections, with a decrease in the level of protective forces (hypothermia [chilling], primary diseases), an inflammatory process develops in the lungs. Most often, the etiology of pneumonia includes diseases of the upper respiratory tract. An inflammatory process can develop in the lungs against the background of respiratory diseases such as flatulence, tracheitis, acute or chronic bronchitis. The cause of the disease may be acute diseases of other organs and systems, complications after surgery, and other factors that have a negative impact on immunity.

Globally, pneumonia is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in children younger than the age of 5 years. Although the majority of deaths attributed to pneumonia in children are mostly in the developing world, the burden of disease is substantial, and there are significant healthcare-associated costs related to pneumonia in the developed world. This activity reviews the cause, pathophysiology, and presentation of pediatric pneumonia and highlights the role of the interprofessional team in its management. In many cases, complaints associated with pneumonia are nonspecific, including cough, fever, tachypnea, and difficulty breathing. Young children may present with abdominal pain.

Important history to obtain includes the duration of symptoms, exposures, travel, sick contacts, baseline health of the child, chronic diseases, recurrent symptoms, choking, immunization history, maternal health, or birth complications in neonates. Physical exam should include observation for signs of respiratory distress, including tachypnea, nasal flaring, lower chest in-drawing, or hypoxia on room air. Note that infants may present with reported inability to tolerate feeds, with grunting or apnea. Auscultation for rales or rhonchi in all lung fields with the appropriately sized stethoscope can also aid in diagnosis. In the developed world, other adjuncts like laboratory testing and imaging can be a helpful part of the physical exam. No isolated physical exam finding can accurately diagnose pneumonia.

However, the combination of symptoms, including fever, tachypnea, focal crackles, and decreased breath sounds together, raises the sensitivity for finding pneumonia on x-ray.[23]

Pneumonia is a clinical diagnosis that should take into consideration the history of present illness, physical exam findings, adjunct testing, and imaging modalities. Pneumonia is an invasion of the lower respiratory tract, below the larynx by pathogens either by inhalation, aspiration, respiratory epithelium invasion, or hematogenous spread. There are barriers to infection that include anatomical structures (nasal hairs, turbinates, epiglottis, cilia), and humoral and cellular immunity. Once these barriers are breached, infection, either by fomite/droplet spread (mostly viruses) or nasopharyngeal colonization (mostly bacterial), results in inflammation and injury or death of surrounding epithelium and alveoli.

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